

BIO-ECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LEPIDOPTERA

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Abstract: The membranous wings of butterflies are covered with small scales. The beautiful color of the wings of butterflies depends on the pigment in these grains. Oral organs consist of a sucking pharynx. Khartoum is worn under the head in a spiral shape. It has a pair of compound eyes and whiskers of various shapes on its head.

Key words: Lepidoptera, coin-winged, *Pieris brassicae*, *Nymphalidae*, *Aparia erataegi*, *Bombyci mori*, *Helionis obsolete*, *Tineidae*.

Butterflies, lepidoptera (Lepidoptera) - a group of insects developed with complete metamorphosis. Originated at the beginning of the Mesozoic Era, the main families were formed at the beginning of the Paleogene. Fossil remains are known mainly from the Cretaceous period. The membranous wings of butterflies are covered with small scales. The beautiful color of the wings of butterflies depends on the pigment in these grains. Oral organs consist of a sucking pharynx. Khartoum is worn under the head in a spiral shape. It has a pair of compound eyes and whiskers of various shapes on its head. In addition to three pairs of chest legs, worms also have 3-5 pairs of false abdominal legs. False legs differ from true walking legs on the chest in that they are not jointed. The larvae of most butterflies live in the open, some species live in the soil and in plant tissues. Adult butterflies feed by sucking flower nectar. Some butterflies have reduced mouthparts and do not feed in adulthood. Worms feed on plant tissue. Among them, there are many species that damage fruit trees and crops. Butterflies are divided into diurnal and nocturnal butterflies according to the time of day they are active. Daytime butterflies fly, feed and breed during the light period of the day. They are distinguished from each other by the fact that they find shelter and hide when they enter late[1]. Biology of the members of the family of pinnipeds. Cockroaches are very common in nature. They include more than 10,000 species. It will be allocated to about 70 families. Below we will introduce the representatives of the main families.

Butterflies of the Pieridae family have pale or yellowish wings. The caterpillars of white butterflies (cabbage butterfly - *Pieris brassicae*) damage cabbage, radish, turnip and other plants belonging to the cabbage family. This family also includes the clear-winged hawthorn butterfly (*Aparia erataegi*). The caterpillar of the butterfly harms the hawthorn tree. In the summer season, nymphalides - large colorful pearl butterflies belonging to the Nymphalidae family and gray velvet butterflies belonging to the Satyridae family are often found in the fields.

Butterflies belonging to the Bombycidae family have not developed oral organs. These butterflies are distributed in tropical climates. The mulberry silkworm (*Bombyci mori*) is raised from them to obtain silk fibers. The mulberry silkworm was domesticated 3.5-5 thousand years ago. It is not found in nature now. It is bred in Central Asia, China, Japan, India, Southern Europe and several other regions. Caterpillars of the Tortricidae family of butterflies feed on leaves or live inside fruits.

Widespread apple fruit borer - *Laspeyresia pomonella* is a small moth, whose caterpillars worm apples, plums, bananas, pears, apricots and cause great damage to horticulture. The butterfly lays about 100 eggs on the leaves. Apple fruit eater develops 2-3 generations in one season. The first generation matures in late spring and early summer, and the second generation in summer.

By autumn, the worms hibernate at the bottom of the tree trunk or in the soil. Butterflies will emerge from them next spring. Noctuidae - Noctuidae is the largest family of butterflies and includes more than 30,000 species. Butterflies are dull, gray or brown in color. Worms are considered a dangerous pest of plants. Autumn cutworm (blueworm) *Agrotis segetum* damages cotton, corn, sunflower and other crops. The bollworm (*Helionis obsolete*) causes great damage to wheat, corn and other crops. Orgyidae butterflies do not have developed proboscis. The body of worms is covered with long hairs.

It feeds on the leaves of various plants. The fungus develops in a thin cocoon under plant debris. The unpaired silkworm (*Ocneria dispar*) causes extensive damage to various fruit and non-fruit trees. Worms of the Tineidae family damage woolen clothing, furniture, grain, and museum collections. The hairs on the head of worms are arranged irregularly. Butterflies are inconspicuous, their mouthparts are not developed[2]. Bio-ecology and characteristics of some pincers included in the Red Book.

A number of unique and decreasing species of the family of moths are included in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Below are the bio-

ecological features of some of its representatives. Status, Distribution, Limiting factors, Conservation measures, a local endemic species of Ferghana, which has disappeared from the face of the earth. Found around Beshariq in the south of Ferghana Valley. Development of dry land in the desert, construction of villages in residential areas. Unseen Weak, naturally rare endemic species of Western TianShan. In Western TianShan, Ugom, Qorjontov, Piskom, Koksuv, Chotkal, Kurama mountain ranges in Uzbekistan: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. As a result of livestock grazing, the number decreases (food plants and worms are trampled), uncontrolled picking of their imagos. It is protected in the Chotkal Reserve and the UgomChotkal National Nature Park. Weak, declining, patchy North Turkestan and South Turkestan Afghanistan subspecies. Western Tien Shan, Western Pamir-Aloy. In Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, the Caucasus region, Western Asia, Southern Europe - other subspecies. Excessive use of pasture and haymaking in cattle breeding, endoparasitism. Chotkal, Nurota Reserve and UgomChotkal National Nature Park are under protection. It is a weak, declining, rare endemic and narrow endemic mountain species. Mountains of Central Asia. In Uzbekistan: Chotkal, Piskom, Ugom, Qorjontov, Kurama mountain ranges, Oloy, as a result of excessive grazing of cattle, their worms and food in the places where these species live are in Hisar and Chotkal reserve and UgomChotkal national

Zarafshan, Turkiston, Baysuntog, Hisar. gathering of plants. protected in the nature park. Southwestern Palaeartic is an endangered subspecies of the species, locally distributed in Iran, South Turkestan. KattaBismil massif on Bobotog mountain. Outside Uzbekistan: Tajikistan, South Turkmenistan and Iran. Destruction of fodder plants due to overuse of pastures in farming (construction) and animal husbandry. It is necessary to protect habitats. Weak, naturally rare, locally distributed southwestern Palaeartic species. Qorjontov, Nurota t.t. Outside Uzbekistan: Kazakhstan and the south of Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, the European part of Russia, Crimea, Caucasus, Turkey. Destruction of habitats due to economic activity, excessive use of pastures. It is protected in Nurota Nature Reserve and UgomChotkal National Nature Park. Weak, declining, patchy South Turonian endemic species. Surkhandarya village, Akkurgan village. and Zarafshan's Samarkand sh. Nearby places. Central Fergana. Destruction of forests and forage plants as a result of economic activity. Zarafshan National Nature Park and Kyzylkum Reserve are protected.

The family of centipedes is the most common family among representatives of the class of insects. Different types of moths are found in different ecological

environments. For example, the leech dragonfly is adapted to live in stagnant water bodies, and the ringed dragonfly is adapted to live in oases. In spite of the diversity of cockroaches, rare and endangered species are also found in nature. This is an urgent problem of today's entomologists. It is necessary to protect butterfly species included in the Red Book by specialists, to help them reproduce on a large scale, to establish special gardens and nurseries for them. The useful species of stilts are used in industry, food, and sewing. Their conservation and protection, and the reproduction of their species will greatly benefit the prospects of our industry

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